

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ELMINA **2018**

PROGRAM

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Rectorate of the University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia
August 27-29, 2018
<http://elmina.tmf.bg.ac.rs>

Organized by:
Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy,
University of Belgrade

Endorsed by:
European Microscopy Society and Federation of European Materials Societies

FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ELMINA 2018
Program and Book of Abstracts

Publisher: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts
Knez Mihailova 35, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
Phone: +381 11 2027200
<https://www.sanu.ac.rs/en/>

Editor: Velimir R. Radmilović and Vuk V. Radmilović

Technical Editor: Vuk V. Radmilović

Cover page: Vuk V. Radmilović

Printed in: Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts
Knez Mihailova 35, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
Phone: +381 11 2027128
stamparija@sanu.ac.rs

Circulation: 50 copies

ISBN 978-86-7025-785-6

Synergistic Anticancer Interaction of Metformin and Caffeine on Fibrosarcoma in Hamsters

Dušica J. Popović¹, Dušan Lalošević¹, Dejan Miljković¹, Kosta J. Popović²,
Ivan Čapo¹, Jovan K. Popović³

¹ Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine,
University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

² Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

³ Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology,
Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

We investigated the effect of metformin and caffeine on fibrosarcoma in hamsters. We were guided by the idea that the use of nontoxic repurposed drugs in arrangement with other medication should be effective against cancer, with decreased toxicity.

Based on the separate *in vitro* evidence of metformin's [1] and caffeine's [2] antifolate activity, we perceived a possible synergistic anticancer effect of these drugs. The finding that caffeine enhanced pemetrexed's antifolate activity in the four studied mesothelioma cell lines was important for our research motivation [2]. Like metformin, caffeine can induce apoptosis in various human cancer cell lines, such as neuroblastoma [3], lung [4] and pancreatic [5] adenocarcinomas, leukemia cells [6] and non-small lung carcinoma [7]. Furthermore, caffeine enhances the toxicity of radiation and sensitivity of cancer cells to chemotherapy [8].

32 Syrian golden hamsters of both sexes, weighing approximately 100 g, were randomly allocated to 3 experimental and 2 control groups, with a minimum of 6 animals per group. 2×10^6 BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously into the animals' back in 4 groups. The first experimental group started peroral treatment with metformin 500 mg/kg daily, the second with caffeine 100 mg/kg daily and the third with a combination of metformin 500 mg/kg and caffeine 100 mg/kg daily, via a gastric probe 3 days before tumor inoculation. After 2 weeks, when the tumors were approximately 2 cm in the control group, all animals were sacrificed. The blood was collected for glucose and other analyses. The tumors were excised and weighted and their diameters were measured. The tumor samples

were pathohistologically (HE) and immunohistochemically (Ki-67, CD 31, COX IV, GLUT-1, iNOS) assessed (Figure 1) and the main organs toxicologically analyzed, including the control animals that had received metformin and caffeine. Tumor volume was determined using the formula $L \times S^2/2$, where L was the longest and S the shortest diameter. Ki-67-positive cells in the tumor samples were quantified. Images were taken and processed by software UTHSCSA Image Tools for Windows Version 3.00. Statistical significances were determined by the Student's *t*-test.

Our results show that the combination of metformin and caffeine inhibited fibrosarcoma growth in hamsters without toxicity.

We concluded that the administration of metformin with caffeine might be an effective and safe approach in novel nontoxic adjuvant anticancer treatment.

References:

- [1] B Corominas-Faja *et al*, *Aging* **4** (2012), 480.
- [2] SH Min, ID Goldman and R Zhao, *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol* **61** (2008), 819.
- [3] MH Jang *et al*. *J Korean Med Sci* **17** (2002), 674.
- [4] W Qi, D Qiao and JD Martinez, *Radiat Res* **157** (2002), 166.
- [5] B Gururajanna *et al*, *Int J Mol Med* **4** (1999), 501.
- [6] Y Dai *et al*, *Cancer Res* **61** (2001), 5106.
- [7] M Hałas *et al*, *Cent Eur J Biol* **9** (2014), 727.
- [8] S Saiki *et al*, *Autophagy* **7** (2011), 176.
- [9] The authors acknowledge funding from the Republic of Serbia, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Provincial Secretariat for High Education and Scientific Research, Grant No. 142-451- 2469/2017 (JP) and Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Grants No. 171039 (BM) and 172013 (SD). The excellent technical assistance and suggestions of el. eng. Mrs. Vesna Popović during the preparation of this work are gratefully acknowledged.

Figure 1. BHK fibrosarcoma: A) mitoses; B) penetration into skeletal striated muscle; C) multiple areas of tumor necrosis; D) tumor vasculature and hemorrhagic areas.